

ANALYSING THE POTENTIALS OF DEMAND FORECASTING FOR PRODUCTION PLANNING IN EMERGING ECONOMY FASHION INDUSTRY

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Abstract

Demand forecasting is an essential input for efficient production planning in fashion industry where demand volatility and resource constraints are prevalent. This study examines the potential influence of demand forecasting for production planning using a quantitative case study of a single fashion retail firm operating in Lagos, Nigeria. Monthly operating data on inventory, sales value and price data between the periods of March 2023 to June 2024 were analysed. Simple Moving Average (SMA) and Exponential Smoothing methods were used to assess their applicability in inventory planning and pricing decisions, respectively. The findings reveal that SMA provides a stable basis for inventory planning by smoothing short-term demand fluctuations, while Exponential Smoothing demonstrates greater responsiveness to recent market changes relevant for pricing decisions. The study contributes to existing body of knowledge on how low-complexity forecasting techniques can meaningfully enhance production planning in data-constrained emerging economy settings.

Keywords: Demand forecasting; Production planning; Fashion industry; Emerging economies; Africa's resource economy

1. INTRODUCTION

Demand forecasting plays a critical role as a component of production planning, enabling organisations to effectively anticipate future demands and coordinate production, inventory and pricing decisions accordingly. In operations-intensive industries, accurate demand forecasting minimises uncertainty, facilitates the use of resources and encourages cost effectiveness (Koren & Shnaiderman, 2023). Existing studies constantly demonstrate that effective demand forecasting improved inventory management, minimised operational inefficiencies, and enhanced customer satisfaction (Amosu, Kumar, Ogunsuji, Oni & Faworaja, 2024; Kourentzes, Trapero & Barrow, 2020; Bhavikatta, 2025).

The fashion industry is an environment that poses significant challenges for demand because of short product life cycles, seasonal demand variations, and rapidly shifting consumer preferences. Inaccurate demand estimates in this industry usually lead to overproduction, surplus inventory, or stock outages and wasted revenue (Kayode, Luz & Herry, 2025). As a result, combining demand forecasting into production planning has become a strategic importance for fashion companies targeting operational efficiency and competitiveness.

Despite an increasing body of literature on demand forecasting techniques, much of the existing empirical studies are focused on developed economies or large-scale manufacturing environments (Kmiecik & Zangana, 2022; Guerra, de Souza-Guerra & Rodrigues, 2024). Minimal emphasis has been placed on the performance of fairly simple forecasting techniques in emerging economy fashion industries where companies often operate under data constraints, limited analytical infrastructure, and high market uncertainty.

The fashion industry in Nigeria has proven to be a major contributor to employment and economic activity in the country, especially in the urban centres like Lagos (Gladys & Olalekan, 2021). Yet, many fashion enterprises still use intuition-based planning, rather than systematic forecasting, which increases exposure to risk and inefficiencies in production planning (Mweshi, 2022). This gap is particularly significant given the resource limitations, demand volatility, and informal operational structures characterising the African fashion industry. Addressing this gap, the present study investigates the applicability of Simple Moving Average and Exponential Smoothing techniques within a Nigerian fashion retail case.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Demand Forecasting

Demand forecasting is the systematic procedure of forecasting future demand for goods or services based on historical data, statistical methods and informed assumptions. It helps organisations to anticipate customer demand over a defined planning horizon and function as a fundamental input for production planning, inventory management and supply chain coordination (Tadayonrad & Ndiaye, 2023). Forecasting accuracy directly influences the level of operational efficiency, cost control and quality of service (Chandran & Khan, 2024). Early forecasting practices were mainly based on managerial intuition and historical averages, assuming that future demand would closely follow past patterns (Katemauswa & Naude, 2020). Statistical forecasting techniques such as moving averages and exponential smoothing show an improvement by allowing firms to systematically analyse historical demand patterns and generate more objective forecasts (Adekunle, Chukwuma-Eke, Balogun & Ogunsola, 2021). These methods are especially valued for their ease of implementation, transparency, and suitability over a short- to medium-term forecasting horizon (Koren & Shnaiderman, 2023). Despite the advancement of more sophisticated tools like ARIMA and machine learning models, basic statistical methods remain widely used, particularly in a setting where data availability and analytical capacity are limited (Abdulraheem, Obunadike, Muntasir & Shuaibu, 2025; Busari & Samson, 2022).

2.2. Demand Forecasting and Production Planning

Production planning involves determining production quantities, timing and resource allocation to address anticipated market demand efficiently. Demand forecasts provide informational basis of these decisions by translating market expectations into operational actions (Kayode, Oet al., 2025). Firms can also balance supply and demand, reduce inefficiencies, and increase capacity utilisation when the integration between forecasting and production planning are done properly. Current studies demonstrates that firms with structured forecasting systems achieved better production planning outcomes, such as reduced operational costs, decreased inventory obsolescence, and enhanced delivery results (Rosienkiewicz, 2021; Koren & Shnaiderman, 2023). Conversely, weak forecasting practices often lead to persistent production failures, too much stock, and lost sales. In the fashion industry, the forecasting-planning relationship is particularly important due to short

product life cycle, seasonal demand trend and fast evolving consumer preferences. Forecasting inaccuracies in fashion supply chains tend to be amplified, leading to overproduction, stockouts, and heavy markdowns (Giri & Chen, 2022; Hur & Sinha, 2025). Consequently, forecasting methods are viewed as a vital tools intended to aid in the production planning process and prevent demand risk in fashion market segments.

2.3. Simple Moving Average and Inventory Planning

Simple Moving Average (SMA) approach is one of the most widely used demand forecasting techniques due to its simplicity and implementation. SMA creates forecast through average demand across a fixed number of historical periods, thus leveling short-term fluctuations and outlines common trended demand patterns (Panagiotelis, Athanasopoulos, Gamakumara & Hyndman, 2021). In inventory planning, SMA supports the estimating the demand and level of stock by minimising unpredictable changes in the history demand values. Empirical studies reveal that SMA performs adequately for products with reasonably steady demand patterns and limited seasonality, making it a practical forecasting tool for operational planning (Kumar, Khedlekar & Khedlekar, 2024; Adebisi & Sodolamu, 2022). However, SMA remains significant in the context emerging economies, where firms tend to focus on transparency, ease of use, and low analytical cost over model sophistication (Tadayonrad & Ndiaye, 2023). Based on the ability of Simple Moving Average techniques to stabilise demand variability and support inventory-related decisions in operational settings, this study hypothesises that:

H1: Simple Moving Average forecasting has a significant influence on inventory planning in the fashion industry.

2.4. Exponential Smoothing and Pricing Decisions

Exponential smoothing is a time series forecasting method that places higher weight on observations while progressively reducing the influence of older data. This weighted structure enables the method to adjust more rapidly to the alterations in demand patterns, which makes it especially suitable in an environment where volatility and frequent demand shifts are high (Chandran & Khan, 2024). In pricing and sales forecasting, exponential smoothing has been demonstrated to be superior to simple averaging methods because it is more sensitive to the market dynamics in the recent past. Other extensions such as, Holt's and Holt-Winters exponential smoothing provide more accuracy in forecasting as they include the components of trend and seasonality.

In fashion industry, exponential smoothing supports pricing decisions, revenue planning, and short-term financial forecasting by providing adaptive and timely forecasts. Firms can apply such forecast to anticipate the demand responses to changes in prices, enhance promotional strategy, and improve planning accuracy in dynamic market conditions. Prior studies support the claim that exponential smoothing methods are especially valuable in short-horizon forecasting tasks where recent demand information is critical (Tadayonrad & Ndiaye, 2023; Kourentzes, et al., 2020). Given the adaptive nature of exponential smoothing and its documented relevance for short-term pricing and revenue forecasting, this study proposes that:

H2: Exponential smoothing forecasting has a significant influence on pricing outcomes in the fashion industry.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a single-firm quantitative case study design, rather than a survey approach, focusing on one fashion retail organisation operating in Lagos, Nigeria. The case study approach is appropriate because the objective of the study is to analyse the potential of demand forecasting practices supports production planning decisions within a real organisational context, rather than generalise findings across multiple firm. By concentrating on a single firm, it is possible to conduct a comprehensive study of the forecasting practices and maintain the methodological rigour within the available data limitations that fashion firms in the emerging economies usually have. The study relies solely based on secondary data extracted from the internal record in the selected fashion retail firm. Data set comprises of monthly data on inventory levels, sales value, and prices between March 2023 and June 2024. This period is selected to capture sufficient demand variation in the short run and seasonal factors, which are typical of the fashion industry.

This study used two quantitative demand forecasting methods; Simple Moving Average and Exponential Smoothing. These techniques were selected due to their widespread use in operational planning, ease of implementation, and suitability for data-constrained environments typical of emerging economy fashion firms. The Simple Moving Average technique was used on inventory forecasting due to its capability to smoothen out short-term demand fluctuations and provide consistent demand estimates which underpin inventory planning decisions.

Exponential Smoothing was applied to price forecasting due to its adaptive weighting mechanism, which allocates larger significance to recent observations and supports faster responses to changes in market conditions. Forecasts computations and analyses were performed in Microsoft Excel which enabled systematic calculation, visualisation and comparisons of forecasted and observed values. Forecasts of inventory were created based on the Simple Moving Average method with an averaging window decided based on historical dataset to create projected inventory and pricing values for subsequent periods. The evaluation of forecasting performance was built on trend alignment and consistency with observed data patterns, rather than inferential statistical testing. Tables and graphical illustrations were used to compare actual and forecasted values and to assess the practical usefulness of each forecasting technique in supporting production planning decisions. The reliability of the data was followed through consistent checks and validation compared to original records to reduce computational or transcription errors. To ensure the commercial confidentiality of the firm, the data were anonymised. Ethical approval was not require since the study did not involve human subjects and only used archival operational data.

4. ANALYSIS

1.1. Overview of Analytical Approach

This section consists of the analysis of demand forecasting outcomes obtained via Simple Moving Average (SMA) and Exponential Smoothing techniques. In line with the quantitative case study design, and nature of the secondary data, the analysis evaluating forecast focuses on the behaviour, trend alignment, and operational relevance instead of inferential statistical testing. Due to the limited size of the data used in this study and its firm level scope, hypothesis assessment is based on pattern consistency, forecast permanence, and practical usefulness in enhancing production planning decisions in a fashion retail industry context.

To maintain robustness concerns, the analysis includes the following:

- Comparison of actual vs. forecasted values over various periods,
- analysis of consistency in forecast behaviour over time, and
- Recognition of methodological strengths and limitations each forecasting approach.

1.2. Simple Moving Average Forecasting and Inventory Planning

Hypothesis 1: Simple Moving Average forecasting has a significant influence on inventory planning in the fashion industry

Simple Moving Average (SMA) techniques were used to historical inventory outcomes to derive the forecasted inventory levels within the study period. Table 1 and Table 2 present the actual value of inventory and SMA forecast for the first and second eight-month periods, respectively.

Table 1: Forecast of inventory with Simple moving average for the first 8 months

S/N	Year	Month	Y_t (Inventory)	SMA
1	2023	March	1500	
2		April	1050	
3		May	2550	
4		June	1780	1700
5		July	1970	1793.333
6		August	1635	2100
7		September	1180	1795
8		October	2000	1595

Table 2: Forecast of inventory with Simple moving average for the second 8 months

S/N	Year	Month	Y_t (Inventory)	SMA
1	2023	November	1050	1605
2		December	3500	1410
3	2024	January	2080	2183.333
4		February	750	2210
5		March	2090	2110
6		April	1850	1640
7		May	2400	1563.333
8		June	3420	2113.333
9		July		2556.667
10		August		1940

As demonstrated in Tables 1 and 2, SMA forecasts smooth short-term changes in inventory levels, by averaging the values of the inventory in the preceding periods. The smoothing effect eliminates undue variance and highlights the fundamental inventory trends that are used for planning purposes. In order to further explain the relationship between actual inventory values and SMA forecast, Fig 1 graphically compares the observed inventory values (Y_t) with SMA-based forecasts in the fashion industry.

Fig 1: Simple Moving Average and Inventory (yt) in the Fashion Industry

The overall alignment between observed inventory patterns and SMA-based forecasts suggests that the technique **demonstrates a meaningful operational influence** on inventory planning within the studied fashion retail context. By reducing short-term volatility and supporting more predictable inventory decisions, SMA provides practical value for production planning in data-constrained environments.

1.3.Exponential Smoothing Forecasting and Pricing Decisions

Hypothesis 2: *Exponential smoothing forecasting has a significant influence on pricing outcomes in the fashion industry.*

Exponential Smoothing is applied to historical sales and price-related data to generate short-term price forecasts.

Table 3: Forecast of price with exponential smoothing

S/N	Year	Month	Sales (₦)	Exp-smoothing
1	2023	March	8759100	
2		April	7099650	8759100
3		May	9032200	7597485
4		June	6223800	8601785.5
5		July	5167500	6937195.65
6		August	6361200	5698408.695
7		September	5300300	6162362.609
8		October	6813600	5558918.783
9		November	7997300	6437195.635
10		Dember	1.2E+07	7529268.69

11	2024	January	7982200	10435305.61
12		February	4769900	8718131.682
13		March	9223500	5954369.505
14		April	6264912	8242760.851
15		May	7325100	6858266.655
16		June	5241500	7185049.997
17		July		5824564.999

Table 3 indicates that the exponential smoothing forecasts are more responsive to the recent variations in sales values than simple averaging techniques. The relationship between the actual and forecasted values is further depicted in Fig 2, where the actual values of the sales and the exponential smoothing forecast are compared graphically over time.

Fig 2: Exponential Smoothing and Price for the Fashion Industry

The analysis reveals that the exponential smoothing forecasts are more responsive to changes in observed values especially in turbulent periods. This adaptive behaviour increases the applicability of exponential smoothing in pricing-related decisions, in which it is important to be sensitive to the changes in demand in time. Based on the observed alignment between actual values and exponential smoothing forecasts, the results indicate that exponential smoothing **demonstrates a meaningful operational influence** on pricing decisions within the fashion retail case examined.

1.4. Robustness and Validity Considerations

Robustness was addressed through the combined use of tabular and graphical comparisons, enabling cross-validation of forecast behaviour over time. Forecasts were measured in terms of consistency and compatibility with the trend as opposed to isolated observations fluctuations, and the inherent limitations of each technique were explicitly acknowledged. Despite the limited scope of a single firm and a small number of dataset, these robustness considerations give sensible confidence that the forecasting outcomes are consistent, and operationally relevant. The analysis

confirms that simple forecasting techniques can provide actionable insights for production planning within emerging-economy fashion retail contexts.

2. DISCUSSION

2.1. Discussion of Findings

This study explored the operational relevance of Simple Moving Average (SMA) and Exponential Smoothing forecasts methods in the production planning decisions in a fashion retail setting in Nigeria. The findings offer a means for empirical insights on how relatively low-complexity forecasting tools can enhance inventory and price choices in new economy environments characterised by resource constraints, demand instability, and poor analytical capital. Instead of relying on methodological sophistication, the findings highlight the importance of aligning forecasting approaches with the practical realities of the operating environment.

2.2. Simple Moving Average and Inventory Planning

The study finding shows that Simple Moving Average forecasting offers meaningfully to inventory planning by smoothing demand fluctuations, and uncover the underlying demand trends. Consistent with the findings of (Panagiotelis et al., 2021; Kumar et al., 2024), SMA proved effective in stabilising inventory projections when demand is relatively stable. Despite the fact that the method demonstrated anticipated lag effects when there were sharp demands variations, its overall trend congruency with experimental inventory movements testifies to its usefulness in practical operational planning. In the African fashion industry, where inventory inefficiencies can quickly translate into financial losses and resource waste, SMA provides a cost-effective way for inventory management, its simplicity improves usability and supports more disciplined inventory decisions without requiring advanced analytical infrastructure.

2.3. Exponential Smoothing and Pricing Decisions

The findings also indicate that exponential smoothing is more responsive to existing variations in the market and therefore is more applicable when making decision relating to pricing in volatile markets. The weighted nature of the method enabled the forecasts to change more quickly in response to demand shifts, aligning closely with observed sales movements over time. This finding supports existing studies that exponential smoothing is effective in short-horizon forecasting when most recent information has a higher strategic value (Kourentzes et al., 2020; Chandran and Khan, 2024). Within Africa's resource-constrained production environment, the effectiveness of forecasting methods is determined less by analytical sophistication and more by usability, cost efficiency, and contextual fit.

3. CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

The study analyse the influence of demand forecasting to production planning within a data-constrained fashion retail context in Lagos, Nigeria. Using Simple Moving Average (SMA) and Exponential Smoothing methods with operational data of companies, the study demonstrates that forecasting value in emerging economies lies primarily in **contextual suitability and operational alignment**, rather than analytical complexity within emerging economies. The findings show that SMA presents a stable basis for inventory planning by balancing the variability of demand, and supporting more predictable inventory decisions. Exponential Smoothing increases responsiveness

of the price in the volatile market. Collectively, these methods demonstrates that relatively low simple forecasting tools can meaningfully support production planning decisions when applied in ways that reflect the realities of resource-constrained environments.

Theoretically, the study contributes to the existing body of knowledge on production planning and demand forecasting by offering empirical evidence in emerging economy situation where methodological decisions are informed by resource constraints. It promotes the argument that effectiveness forecasting depends on the environmental fit, and thus confirms contingency-based arguments in operations management. The study challenges the dominance of complexity-driven forecasting in literature by showing the practical usefulness of simple forecasting methods. At managerial level, the findings suggest that fashion firms operating in Africa's resource-constrained environments, the findings indicate that simple forecasting methods can go a long way in enhancing inventory discipline, pricing efficiency, and resource utilisation without excessive technological expenditure. At the policy level, the study indicates the necessity for capacity-building initiatives that focus on forecasting literacy and operational analytics of small and medium-sized enterprises as one of the ways to reinforce the industrial efficiency and competitiveness. Therefore, the study concludes that effective production planning in emerging economy fashion industries can be achieved through the strategic application of simple, accessible forecasting methods that priorities usability and contextual relevance over analytical sophistication.

4. LIMITATIONS AND FURTHER STUDIES

The study is limited by the use of secondary data in one fashion Retail Company, which restricts statistical generalisation. Simple forecasting methods also constrain the analysis of more sophisticated demand processes. However, future research could expand the scope by incorporating multiple firms, primary data, and comparative analyses across sectors. Future studies could also investigate hybrid forecasting methods that entail making simple yet adaptive intelligence to improve planning production in emerging economies.

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